

MICRO AND SMALL BUSINESS AND GOVERNMENT SUPPORT POLICY IN GEORGIA

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Georgia is the leading country in the Caucasus region in terms of reforms, economic development and progressive democratic institutions. The priority of the country is to pass the path of Euro-Atlantic integration and offer investors a favorable environment for doing business, and to establish relationships with the subjects beyond the borders.

Key-words: *Georgia, economy, Caucasus region, borders.*

Georgia is geographically located at the crossroads of Europe and Asia and is the shortest transport route between the two regions. The unique and strategic location of the country allows for the use of growing trade flows between the European, Caspian, Central, and East Asian countries. One of the lowest and easy-to-manage tax regimes in Georgia, political stability, improved business climate with low operating costs and the business-oriented government is creating an attractive environment for investments across the country.

After signing the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area Agreement with the European Union, Georgia is actively pursuing its efforts to move towards EU integration.

Over the last two years, Georgia has

experienced significant economic progress. According to the World Bank forecasts, the annual GDP indicator will increase by 5% over the next few years, creating a prospect of Georgia as one of the fastest-growing economies in the world.

The agreement on the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area Agreement between Georgia and the European Union allows Georgia to conduct part of the EU market (which includes 500 million people), and with the free trade agreement with Turkey and other neighboring countries and CIS countries, Georgia offers access to the EU market. In addition, Georgia has signed GSP (preferential trade agreement) trade agreements with the United States, Japan, Canada, Switzerland and Norway.

The number of direct foreign investments is also increasing in Georgia. At

the same time, the production, which contributes more than 17% of GDP, represents an important driving force for economic development of the country. In fact, in the last five years production has grown an average annual 19% growth. In 2014, agriculture sector grew by almost 10% and industrial products - by about 7%. As for the transport and communications sector, it has increased by 13% since 2009 and accounts for almost 11% of GDP.

Georgia is consistently ranked as the TOP performer in country policy and institutional assessments (CPIA) compiled by international financial institutions (WB, ADB etc.)

- Standard & Poor's: BB- Stable (Affirmed in May 2014)

- Moody's: Ba3 Positive (Affirmed in August 2014)

- Fitch Rating: BB- Positive (Affirmed in October 2014)

- The Heritage Foundation ranked Georgia the 22nd among 178 countries Economic Freedom Ranking

Corruption Free

According to the Transparency International Global Corruption Barometer Georgia is perceived as a corruption free destination.

Best Place to Start a Business

Georgia is in top 15 best Doing Business Destinations according to World Bank.

Reasonable Tax Policy

According to 2009 Tax Misery & Reform Index, released by Forbes Business &

Financial News, Georgia is the fourth least tax burden country after Qatar, UAE and Hong Kong.

Strategic location

Located at the crossroads of Europe, Central Asia, Middle East and Africa Georgia is a key link in the shortest transit route between Western Europe and Central Asia for transportation of oil and gas as well as dry cargo.

Stable macroeconomic environment

In recent years, Georgian GDP has growth tendency.

Liberal and free market oriented economic policy

The Government of Georgia implemented reforms in tariff policy as well as in technical regulations sphere. As a result, Georgia has one of the most liberal foreign trade policies in the world, which implies the facilitated foreign trade regimes and customs procedures, low import tariffs and minimal non-tariff regulations.

Developed infrastructure

One of the top priorities for the Government of Georgia is coordinated functioning of transport fields, modernization-construction of transport infrastructure in accordance with international standards. The Government of Georgia is being implementing important infrastructure projects, which shall facilitate new cargo volumes through Georgia and increase effectiveness of functioning of transport systems.

Enhanced Economic Prospects

Signing of the Association Agreement

with European Union will encourage improvements in the rule of law and in effective governance, as well as further moves towards a well-functioning market economy through the removal of tariff and non-tariff barriers.

Key Economic Sectorial Overview:

Industrial Manufacturing and Processing

Georgia provides significant investment opportunities in manufacturing sector, which has attracted more than USD 0.5 billion foreign direct investments since 2010 - 2014*. New opportunities are expected to be grasped by Greenfield investments in export oriented manufacturing sectors, for which access to the European market would be attractive. The share of industry sector in Georgia's GDP is 17.1% in 2014*.

There are significant business opportunities in processing of the primary agricultural goods into a higher value added products and supplying equipment and services (greenhouses, storage, deep-freeze facilities, packaging etc.). Georgian agriculture offers foreign businesses the opportunity to invest in areas of unmet market demand, significant cost efficiencies and strong profit potential.

Tourism and Retail Sector

Tourism is another field, which witnessed significant growth in recent years and is considered to be an important driver of economic development and the creator of jobs as well as generator of revenues. The industry offers a wide diversification in

terms of its sub-industries: summer sea resorts, four season mountain resorts (including skiing), spa-wellness, gaming and more. In fact, from 2003 year to 2014 the number of international visitors to Georgia has increased from 300 thousand to 5,5 million.

According to Hotel Market Report, prepared by Colliers International, the highest average occupancy rates in Tbilisi are in international midscale brand hotels 75% and in international upscale brand hotels 74%. In addition, the ADR (Average Daily Rate) for International upscale hotels is - 203 USD.

With 17.4% of National GDP in 2014, trade is one of the largest economic sectors in Georgia. Annual per capita retail expenditure has doubled over the past decade. More than 9% out of total international visitors visited Georgia for shopping purposes in 2013 year.

Energy Sector

Energy sector is attractive from the perspective of both existing natural resources and developing infrastructure, as the country possesses huge hydro resources and offers untapped potential for investment. For the last years, Georgian has become net exporter of electricity and currently utilizes only 18% of its vast hydro resources. Georgian power grid is connected to the grids of all of neighboring countries, which are faced with either a structural power deficit or expensive power generation. From 2010 to 2014* Georgian energy sector has attracted almost USD 750 mln.

Transport and Logistics

Georgia is in a highly strategic location: It serves as an entry gate to the Caucasus and Central Asia as well as a stepping stone to the region. The country is the shortest route between the Black Sea and the Caspian Sea region. Construction of Baku-Tbilisi-Kars new railway line is on the final stage and it will further advance trade of goods in the whole region. The government is investing heavily in the development of road

infrastructure-highways as well as local roads. At this stage, the government has negotiations with potential investors to build a new deep sea port in Anaklia on Black sea, with an ability to receive vessels of at least 6,500 TEU capacity. The new port will bring Georgia's logistical capabilities to a new level. Therefore, Georgia wants and can be the best place for regional offices, regional stocks, and a part of various value chains.

Area:	69,700 sq. km
Population(2015)	4.5mln
Life expectancy:	76 years
Official language:	Georgian
Literacy:	99.7%
Capital:	Tbilisi
Currency (code)	Lari (GEL)
GDP (2014*)	US \$ 16.5 b.
GDP real growth rate (2014*)	4.7%
GDP per capita (2014*)	USD 3 680.8
FDI Inflows (2014*)	USD \$1 272.5 mln
Unemployment Rate 2013	14.6%
External Trade Turnover Growth in 2014	5 %

The existence of such potential of Georgia's economic growth has led to the Prime Minister's initiative, implemented by the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development and Agriculture for two years already within the framework of the program „Produce Georgia“, which is directed

towards development and promotion.

It should be noted that according to the data of April 2017, 246 projects are supported by the program „Produce Georgia“, with total investment of more than 565 000 000 GEL and totally 11,000 people will be employed.

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